

Review Article

Library Users' Education in the 21st Century

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Abstract

This study attempted to explain the concept of users' education in the 21st Century, the objectives, importance and benefit of users' education as only means of making users' to recognized library as a primary source of Information. It attempted to explain the roles of digital libraries, the objectives and importance of digital libraries as way by which the libraries can be transformed in order to remain relevant and function properly in the 21st century. The study concluded that library staff and Librarians of the 21st century must be an expert and skillful in their professional job so that they can provide users' education extensively. There is a recommendation that Government should implement National policy related to the library, training and re-training of librarians and library staffs in order for them to keep fit and relevant in the 21st century. Finally, librarians of the 21st century should be more focused on digital or virtual libraries to remain relevant in the area of information management.

Keywords: Education, Users' Education, Library and Digital or Virtual Libraries.

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Introduction

Education is generally believed to be the life – line of any society as no society can grow beyond its education curriculum. Also Education is a tool used to develop the individual for his/her own benefit and the benefit of the society at large.

Effectiveness of library as an instrument of education is determined by the success which the library is able to provide and satisfy users' information needs .The library is central to the provision of the right type of information resources that empowers the educational institution to produce highly resourceful people to impact positively in national development. Libraries are established to support the educational curriculum of Schools. This is usually achieved through various means as –the provision of relevant /related resources, which are in line with the provision of various information services ranging from technical to reader's service and lots more.

According to Opeke (2004), Information has received a wide spread acceptance as the essentials features of production, consumption and exchange in this modern era.

Dramatic change in technology and society are having a considerable impact on Libraries and their instructional programs. These changes have created an urgency to teach users' how to become more effective, efficient and independent in their information searching. Users' education is an academic programme that is designed by institutions on how to educate library users' has to be more effective and denoting ways of imparting knowledge on library users' on how to effectively utilized library resources.

Literature Review

Meaning and objective of library users' Education in the 21st century

Users Education encompasses all the activity undertaken to help students become efficient users of information i.e. how to find, evaluate and select the best information to meet that need.

Prytherch (1990) defined users' education as a programme of information provided by librarians to users to enable them make more efficient, independent use of the Library's stocks and services. Aina (2004), is of opinion that users get any information he/she desires as well developing the skill to use the resources of the library independently on any aspect of knowledge by using traditional and electronic method.

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Edoka (2000), assert that the objectives of users education is to help the users make the best use of overall library resources .Also, He enumerated the specific aims of users education includes the following:(i) to develop readers awareness of all overall information resources available to them in their own and other libraries,(ii)to develop skills necessary for retrieving required materials, (iii)to develop in - depth knowledge materials in readers subject areas, (iv)to develop skills in presenting bibliographic references (V) to developed skills in required making advanced studies, (vi)to create a positive attitude to information searching which will stimulate the users to make use of the resource available at different libraries.

Chopral (2001) quoting Tocattlian Jacques (the former Director General, information Programme of UNESCO) defines user's education in generic form as any effort or programme which will guide and instruct existing and potential users of individual or collectively. Chopral (2001) opines that generally users' education includes the following four inter-related components: (a) Users awareness (b) Library Orientation ;(c) Bibliographic instruction and (d) Interest Profiling (users' profile). He is of the view that users awareness aims to information and as an agency to which users may turn for assistance with their information needs.

In the view of Agwuanyi (1998) Library is an Institution or establishment for the care of collection of books and of making them accessible for prospective users. Anybody coming into the library comes with the aims of satisfying his information curiosity that is to have his uncertainty removed. To have this realized presupposes that relevant and adequate information materials are available and as the same time, accessible to users. Library seems to be only ideal place where this expectation could be met.

Akinwumi (1986) observed that users education help in improving the scope and efficiency of information services to them and to derive maximum benefit from the library.

Muogilim (1998) defined users' education as a process of making library patrons to learn how to make effective and efficient use of the library and information resources.

Library users' education in the 21st century should be powered by information in all ramifications. This 21st century age is information explosion in the internet and its associated technologies are being used to take advantage for the benefit of the accelerated development of society. The 21st century users' education should be the education given

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to the users in digital format and not only as a formal program me of instruction given to them before, this enhanced the effort of the library and information managers in rendering more useful contribution in the 21st century. It is therefore and meaningful to suggest that for the library and information manager to continue to be a living force in the advancement of information literacy in the 21st century, Government should ensure the implementation of National policy relates to the library and the training and re-training of librarians and library assistances.

Objectives of Users Education.

- To develop skills necessary for retrieving required materials.
- To help the users make the best use of overall library resources.
- To develop skills in presenting bibliographic references.
- To develop in depth knowledge materials in readers subject areas.
- To create a positive attitude to information searching which will stimulate the users to make use of the resource available at different libraries.
- To develop readers awareness of the overall information resources available to them in their own and other libraries.

Importance of Library Users Education in the 21st Century.

Having defined library users education and its major objectives, the major issue or question to ask is the how important is library users education? Does it make any impact on how people use information? Does it has any effect on users' ways of reading? There is a strong belief that effective use of information is important. It is widely recognized that the ability to use information is extremely important in today's society most especially in this 21st century era where libraries have shifted been from traditional libraries to digital libraries.

The followings are the importance of library users' education.

- I. It enables the users to be familiar with the library resources and its services.
- II. Educating the library users to find, evaluate and select the best information to meet their needs.
- III. It instructs the users on how to be more efficient, effective and independent in their information searching.
- IV. Promotes reading culture among the library users because libraries are normally known to encourage reading.
- V. It also promotes exhibition and displays. Users' education makes readers aware of what is available in the library.

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Roles of Digital Library in Users' Education in the 21st Century.

Online Dictionary for library and Information (2007) Define a Digital library as a library in which a significant proportion of the resources are available in machine format accessible by means of computer.

Association of Research of Libraries (ARL) (1995) Defines Digital libraries as libraries whose collection are all stored in digital format and accessible via computer, the internet e.t.c This digital content can be stored locally or be accessible. ARL (1995) further and therefore required technology to link the resources of many, the linkage between digital libraries and information services are transparent to end users, also digital library collections are not limited to document surrogates and therefore extends to digital artifacts format. With the above description by Association of Research Libraries (1995), it suggest that digital Library can also be referred to as an electronic Library or Virtual Library since their collection are both accessed electronically via internet resources.

Mohammed (2003) defined the term virtual or Digital Library an organized collection of documented information resources not limited by physical structure and printed format but also including electronically stored information and information resources accessed physically and remotely irrespective of the time and the location of the users and /or the information resources with the assistance of the information communication.

Daniel (2002) defined it as a collection of library resources in electronic /digital format at various locations which can be assessed and used with great ease using computer and telecommunication technologies for the purpose of teaching, study, research, learning ,leisure and decision - making.

Omolayole (2002) described a Digital or Virtual Libraries as a system by which users' access information that resides solely in electronic format, on computer networks without respect to physical location of the Information.

Association of Research Libraries (1995) has also identified the following features as common to these definitions: (i) the digital library is not a single entity (ii) the digital library required technology to link resources of many, (iii) the linkages between the many digital libraries and information services are transparent to the end users (iv) Universal access to digital libraries and information service is a goal and (v) digital Libraries' collections are not limited to document surrogates.

Digital library provides access to tools such as database, electronic journals, alerting services, electronic reference and quality -vetted e -resources. The significant advantage of digital library is that it does not require large expensive building to house the acres of shelving needed to store print documents. It is a library that, in theory, offers access to anything in any digital format, at any place. It is also a library that comes directly into the home or office of each library users. The above gives the opportunity to digital or virtual library over the traditional library. Digital information is changing the role of libraries in the 21st century from a person whom students ask for assistance in finding information in a place called a school library to someone who needs to provide services and instruction regardless of place, time or format (Obadare, 2008).

Libraries of 21st century must be modern day library which must be in digital format and be sound in the storage, retrieval and dissemination of information with the aid of information and communication technology (ICT). Library users have to be trained on in - house style or the arrangement and location of most of these gadgets in the library or information centre. This approach would encourage an effective and efficient flow of information from the librarians to the users. Users Education is equally paramount if we expect optimal utilization of library resources and overall maintenance of (ICT) equipment because of their huge cost (Obadare, 2008).

Importance or Benefit of Digital Library

- i. The resources will never be out on loan and will be available at anytime, anyplace and anywhere.
- ii. Access is provided to more complete set of journals than, in many instances, now exist on many library shelves.
- iii. Technical services cost of tracking the arrival of each journal issue, claiming and periodical binding will eliminated.
- iv. The need for added library space may decline.
- v. Cost of retrieving and re-shelving materials will be reduces.

The present day libraries should focus more on the area of digital, virtual or e- library unlike before when their major resources and services focus only on manual. The digital Libraries have transformed libraries and dramatically change their way of offered their resources to the users because most of their resources and services come on digital format which is easier for the library users to access the computer. The library of 21st century must digitize their services and resources through appropriate information and communication technology (ICTS) in order to remain relevant and functions properly in

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the 21st century. With the role and position of libraries, it should focus on digital format in offered better services to their users. However, the traditional or manual way of accessing information in the library is still relevant but more should be concentrating on digital format.

Objectives of Digital Library in the 21st Century Libraries

- i. To enhance the access of academics libraries serving higher educational communities in Nigeria to global library and information resources.
- ii. To improve quality teaching and research in institution of higher learning through the provision of current books journals and other library resources.
- iii. To enhance scholarship, research and life learning through the establishment of permanent access to shared digital archival collections.
- iv. To provide guidance to academics libraries on applying appropriate technologies used in the production of digital libraries research.
- v. To advance the use and usability of globally distributed network of library resources .([http://w.w.w.nuc.edu.ng/DICT/about-DICT htm](http://w.w.w.nuc.edu.ng/DICT/about-DICT.htm)).

With all these points above, the library users of the 21st century would have access to library resources and other library publication online, database on the web with the internet, Libraries and Librarians of the 21st century will even become more valuable and relevant in the area of knowledge, management process and they become crucial partners in learning, nation building and development.

Librarians in the 21st century must be ready to take a new challenge and articulate the need for a new role that will convince the users that library remains the information and literacy access point they need to succeed in the 21st century information society.

Conclusion and Recommendation

For library service to keep pace with the needs of students and other library users in the 21st century, libraries should employ expert and skillful librarian who can provide users education extensively. There is need for library of 21st century to run their services to library users through digital or virtual format not mere on traditional ways which their used before to render services to the users. There is a suggestion that Government should implement policy relate to the library and also there should be constant training and re-training of librarian and library Assistance in order to keep fit in the 21st century age.

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Review Article

Role of Libraries in 21st Century

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Abstract

Libraries have existed for hundreds of years but in today's digital world, where we have at our fingertips access to an endless collection of information, a new standard of information literacy has emerged. Libraries are collections of books and other information resources gathered for the purposes of reading, study, and reference. A library as a collection or group of collections of books and/or other materials organized and maintained for use. Historically, libraries have served as places. The new role of libraries in the 21st century is to be a learning and knowledge center for their users as well as the intellectual commons for their respective communities where, to borrow the phrase from the Keystone Principles, people and ideas interact in both the real and virtual environments to expand learning and facilitate the creation of new knowledge. Libraries preserve knowledge so that none is lost, organize knowledge so that none is wasted, and make knowledge available so that no one need be deprived in this information age. Library services have brought a lot of changes to library operations there by making access to knowledge more convenient to user.

Key words: libraries, knowledge and learning, collection of information, information literacy.

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Introduction

Library/information educational programmes have a long and distinguished history. In the past, they have focused on developing physical collections of books and other materials in library buildings staffed by people who have learned to select, acquire, organise, retrieve and circulate these materials. Today library information educational programmes extend beyond the physical collections and buildings to the virtual world of the Internet. Today the concentration is on information provision to users in a variety of contexts, public, private and third sector; users who may not be necessarily able or willing to enter the library building or environment. Educational programmes are offered at the technical level, at the graduate and professional level, and at the research and doctoral level. The guidelines offered here primarily address the graduate and undergraduate levels, both of which lead to professional qualification.

Libraries are service organizations where individuals, organizations, and societies are provided unhindered access to substantial quantities of information. Libraries are collections of books and other information resources gathered for the purposes of reading, study, and reference. A library as a collection or group of collections of books and/or other materials organized and maintained for use. Historically, libraries have served as places where books used for the documentation of knowledge were kept, but they are now portals to global information relevant in education, research, individual and national development expressed either in formal or systematic language, codified in form of data, scientific formulae, etc.

The library, as a conduit for information, serving a wide spectrum of information seekers, has a critical role to play in the facilitation of knowledge generation; hence, an unhindered access to knowledge is essential in a development process.

Library: Center of Knowledge and Learning

According to Lee (2005), while the business world is changing in the new knowledge economy and digital age, libraries of all types are undergoing drastic changes also. The new role of libraries in the 21st century is to be a learning and knowledge center for their users as well as the intellectual commons for their respective communities where, to borrow the phrase from the Keystone Principles, people and ideas interact in both the real and virtual environments to expand learning and facilitate the creation of new knowledge. As a learning organization, libraries should provide a strong leadership in

knowledge management since the most important mission is to expand the access of knowledge for their users.

The importance of library to knowledge distribution can be facilitated by library services in a variety of ways, which are itemized below (Lee 2005)

- Knowledge resources management: As a result of exponential growth in human knowledge in a variety of formats, libraries must develop their resources access and sharing strategies from printed to electronic and digital resources in concert with their mission and charges;
- Resource sharing and networking: Libraries have had a long tradition of resource sharing and networking. These have been greatly expanded by the rapid development of computer, telecommunication, networking, and digital technologies and the success of which are largely as a result of the full cooperation and participation of all member libraries.
- Information technology development: To facilitate the implementation of knowledge management, a well-designed and operational knowledge management system should be in place. Latest information technology should be used as an enabler.
- User services: The utmost goal of knowledge management is to provide users with a variety of quality services in order to improve the communication, use and creation of knowledge.
- Human resource management: A great amount of expert knowledge is possessed by library staff and users, both in and outside the libraries. In university and research communities such expertise is abundant and should be inventoried, indexed, and updated regularly and be made searchable and accessible through electronic databases created and maintained by libraries. Also the transfer of knowledge and experience from experienced staff to new staff members must be encouraged.

In a nutshell, libraries preserve knowledge so that none is lost, organize knowledge so that none is wasted, and make knowledge available so that no one need be deprived in this information age.

Libraries a Bulk Storage of Knowledge in the 21st Century

Libraries have existed for hundreds of years but in today's digital world, where we have at our fingertips access to an endless collection of information, a new standard of information literacy has emerged.

The ability to connect to and search the Internet has changed the foundation of our society. Reading news stories, shopping, seeking health advice, using email to communicate, etc., have all seen revolutionary changes.

Since the beginning of the Internet, and especially since the year 2000, much was written about the changing environmental landscape and the impact it would have on libraries. The impact of the availability of full text electronic resources at a library, the library's staff and their skills, their organization or even their purpose has been well documented. This was seen primarily in the fields of science, technology and medicine.

Libraries, as critical providers of information, have an important role to play in the creation of new knowledge, arguing further that knowledge is functional at many levels. As knowledge institutions, libraries provide spaces for information-sharing and learning for all ages, genders, ethnicities, and socioeconomic groups regardless of their needs. Libraries provide the means through which new knowledge is developed and made available to all.

Technology and Library Services in the 21st Century

It is an established fact that libraries are driving access to knowledge, the question then is, why the emphasis on 21st century? Why is the 21st century different from past centuries? The truth is that, the 21st century is revolutionized by advances in computing and telecommunication technology. The 21st century has witnessed a great increase in information management and transmission. Our library learning spaces are designated Tran's disciplinary media spaces that give teachers the opportunity to conduct lessons with all of the advantages of the latest technology, and our automated library systems free up time for library professionals to focus on providing personalized assistance to students.

The new information age has brought about improved knowledge delivery, processing of information, precision, good time management and improved network system. Furthermore, information is also called data and databases are created and made accessible online via the Internet and other machine readable formats. Search engines are

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made accessible to the public. In view of this, conventional libraries seem to be giving way to hybrid and virtual libraries. (Otherwise called libraries without walls or paperless libraries) accessing or developing digital collections alongside print-based collections. We are equipping our students with the tools to gain knowledge for themselves, cultivating curiosity and inspiring life-long learning, so that they may be, now and in the future, inquisitive, judicious and informed. If education is life, libraries give us immortality.

Library services have brought a lot of changes to library operations there by making access to knowledge more convenient to user. Some of the fastest growing trends are noticed in the area of networking; file storage, graphic user interface. They have also been enabled by agreements on standards and protocols (such as Z39.50) which permit the linking together of resources from disparate sources.

- **From Multiple Locations:** From anywhere, users can consult all library holdings from workstation throughout the systematic catalog, indexing, and abstracting services. Divorcing library services from a physical location provokes a profound difference in what a library service is.
- **Availability of More Resources:** Technology now allow users to have access to diverse resources i.e. from pure bibliographical records(online catalog) now to delivery of indexing and abstracting services, course descriptions, class schedule.
- **Making Information Available in Raw Form:** Types of information available to users in digital form has continued to grow. In indexing and abstracting; search has moved from providing searchable index terms/descriptors to searchable abstracts, to more recently full-text of articles and books. In the library catalog, we have moved from bibliographic description and subject headings to providing tables of contents information, to full-text and page images. Technology has moved patrons to rawer information or more detailed representation often called enhanced records and has been a key element for those studying information retrieval.
- **Diminishing Roles for Intermediaries:** Increase interaction with online system means patron less reliance upon library staff. Patrons can check circulation information without ever contacting the circulation department.

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Challenges and Recommendations

The birth of ICT actually changed the place of libraries in terms of information acquisition and storage as well as the methods of rendering services. Despite the beautiful development, there exist basic challenges that tend to hinder the provision of access to knowledge by library. These challenges include:

- Apathy on the part of staff: Many library staff tend have an apathetic attitude towards work. They are not committed to client-oriented service.
- Lack of Maintenance Culture: Lack of maintenance culture renders infrastructures and equipment like ICT facilities non-functional.
- Poor Funding: This is the key to effective management as long as such funds are judiciously used.

The following recommendations are made to improve access to information resources in the library.

- There should be training and re-training of librarians and ICT staff in the area of computer technology and management of information services.
- The institution and library managers should be committed and work round the clock to ensure that ICT equipment and facilities are maintained regularly.
- Finally, adequate funds should be provided to ensure effective library operations.

Conclusion

There is no doubt that access to knowledge is critical for the development and growth of the society and for participation in democratic processes. The library is an integral part of the society that surrounds it. It is shaped and changed by many of the same forces that shape other types of institution. Librarians need to recognize the changes that have already taken place in libraries, and to be aware of the ways in which broader societal changes are affecting other institution. Igwe (2010) concluded that libraries provide access to an endless variety of information resources and opportunities for interactive communication. Though the fundamental mission has remained, to facilitate and give access to information and knowledge, the processes, tools and techniques have

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undergone remarkable changes. However, access alone is of course not enough, it is also about extending services, methods, and practices and developing innovative approaches to guarantee free and universal access to relevant knowledge. Libraries should ensure that the world's citizenry have access to the world's knowledge.

The library today, is a technologically driven one that uses the principles of traditional library services to organize knowledge and communicate same to clients in the global community essentially by electronic means.

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